

COVID-19 Economical Impact in the US Stock Market

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Abstract

When the novel coronavirus first hit the United State it left a massive mark in the American economy. We can best view this by comparing all mainstream stock prices before and after March. Due to unpopular belief the biggest winners of this economic downfall are people who began selling stocks and created new business during this pandemic.

Keywords: COVID, America, Stocks, Economy

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Celebrating historic stock market records Donald Trump's Economy was at its all time high. One of the main driving points for his re-election campaign was his economical impact. This great economy has crumbled under a single foreign virus- The SARS-CoV-2. Although the COVID pandemic left millions unemployed and diminished the lives of many people there are some winners of this and it happens to be the people who utilized the stock market at its all time low.

Method

In this paper we analyze the stock market before and after the Coronavirus scare. Although at the time of publishing this there is no official coronavirus cure the fear installed by the public is one of the main reasons the economy went down hill, the United States does not have this problem anymore which is a positive/negative depending on how you view it.

In this analysis I use the chart of the S&P 500 Index, Dow Jones Industrial Average, and the Nasdaq Composite. A similarity between these three that they are a stock market index. A stock market index is an index that measures the stock market. This arguably one of the best concepts to understand when starting out as an investor.

Assessments and Measures

For this analysis we will use March 23rd of 2020 as an index to compare all three of these indexes. In March it is deemed as the month that the economy had a crash labeled as the 2020 stock market crashed by various sources.

Visual Representation of DOW JONES INDUSTRIAL AVERAGE INDEX (TradingView)

For the DOW Jones from February it was cruising at an all time high. However as coronavirus began to popularize in the United States the largest drop from the DOW Jones in 2020 occurred. In February it was averaging a little over \$29,000 when COVID came it dropped to \$18,000 this was roughly a \$11,000 drop. This was a very bad time period to be a stock investor if you had money in the DOW. The smartest option was to not sell your shares and wait till it recovers so you can make at least even when fear is a factor in the equation the thought process of such becomes blocked. It is obvious that this drop affected investors and business but this also enraged the political community. The DOW in a short period of time lost all points gained from the 2016 election which stirred up debate on how the GOP is dealing with the economy and both parties are to blame for not uniting to help the American People.

Visual Representation of the S&P 500 INDEX (Trading View)

Like the DOW the S&P 500 INDEX has faced a terrible crash. In February the index was hovering at around above \$3,000. After the market crashed it was \$2,200. At first this does not seem as bad as the DOW but it carried the same amount of impact. When an index drops down it shows that the stock market is not a safe place to put money in. This results in a chain reaction affecting all stocks in the market. On the bright side in the time of publishing this the S&P 500 INDEX has almost gone to normal.

Visual Representation of the NASDAQ COMPOSITE INDEX (Trading View)

In all stock market indexes viewed in this analysis the current market has not matched with the Indexes all time high-however the NASDAQ COMPOSITE INDEX is an exception. Before the fear outbreak of COVID the stocks all time high in the month of february was roughly \$9,800. COVID made this high number down to roughly \$6,800. This feared many investors because of the main fact that the NASDAQ was one of the safest and well performing Index that was friendly for the everyday budget. However financial experts are telling us not to worry due to the fact that this crash is always temporary and a crash/recession is never finalized.

Results

In conclusion covid 19 had a massive economical impact in the US Stock Market in this paper we analyze the top performing Indexes. With results like this we should always remember not to worry about crashes like this if you are the everyday person due to the fact that your stocks will rise to normal and outperform.